

Food Procurement and Provision in Early Years Settings:

A Yorkshire Case Study

Food Procurement and Provision in Early Years Settings:

A Yorkshire Case Study

Written by **Dayna Brackley** and **Cressida Pidgeon** (Bremner & Co),
Annie Connolly (The Food Foundation), **Maria Bryant** and **Bob Doherty** (FixOurFood)

FixOurFood

FixOurFood is a multi-disciplinary research programme, anchored at the University of York, which aims to transform the Yorkshire food system to one that is regenerative – benefitting both human and planetary health.

w. fixourfood.org

Bremner & Co.

Bremner & Co work to make the food system fairer. They focus on improving food policy and practice so that everyone has the right to good, nutritious, healthy food. Much of their work centres on child health and nutrition across the life course.

w. bremnerco.com

The Food Foundation

The Food Foundation is changing food policy and business practice to ensure everyone, across the UK nations, can afford and access a healthy and sustainable diet.

w. foodfoundation.org.uk

Glossary and information

EY: Early Years

EYS: Early Years Settings

EYFS: Early Years Foundation Stage Framework

FOF: FixOurFood

FSA: Food Standards Agency

FSM: Free School Meals

NCMP: National Child Measurement Programme

PVI: Private and Voluntary Institutions

Food supply chain: The processes and activities that take food from farm to fork. Supply chains can include the following members - producers, manufacturers, logistics, retail, food services, the government, local authorities, schools and early years settings.

Early Years Free School Meals: Children in early years state-maintained settings, who attend before and after lunch, can access free school meals under the same eligibility criteria as school-aged children.

Contents

Executive summary	6
Background	8
EY nutrition policy inertia	8
A fragmented sector operating in crisis	9
Research approach and aims	10
Methodology	11
Section 1: Findings	12
1.1 Yorkshire child health, prosperity and inequality	13
1.2 Yorkshire settings and food provision	14
1.3 EY nutrition is lower on the agenda	15
1.4 Inequality of access	16
1.5 What are children eating in EYS and how is it monitored?	17
Evidence and data gaps about nutrition in the EY	17
1.6 The complex EY supply chain	19
1.7 Funding and food costs	20
Lack of funding and cost of food hampers	20
1.8 Scalability and supplier sourcing – ‘It’s just easier to get it from Tesco’	22
Settings find local supply chains hard to access	22
1.9 Tendering and procurement	23
Operational barriers prevent the procurement of locally sourced food	23
1.10 Staffing/resources	25
Workforce crisis impacts settings ability to focus on EY	25
1.11 Child and parent preference and feeding children	26
Child and parent preferences impact appetite for locally sourced food	26
1.12 The language of provenance and local food	27
Is it local enough?	27

Contents

Section 2: Menu analysis	28
How do nursery menus help us increase our understanding of the procurement journey and provision?	28
Section 3: Barriers and enablers to the procurement of locally sourced, nutritious, affordable Yorkshire food	30
Section 4: Conclusions	31
Section 5: Policy and research recommendations	32
Section 6: Limitations	34
References	35
Acknowledgements	38

Executive summary

Background:

Food procurement in schools and early years settings (EYS) has long been viewed as an opportunity to transform food systems. The FixOurFood programme has identified that food procurement in these settings, (which both prioritises child health and benefits the environment) is an important area needing transformation.¹ However, it acknowledges that the focus of policy and research has been on school-age children, leaving a gap in research on how food is procured in the early years (EY). This report seeks to address this gap in how and what foods are provided in settings that care for children aged five years and under. It is a continuation of FixOurFood's work on public sector food procurement in schools.¹

Evidence suggests that good nutrition and health in the EY plays a fundamental role in a child's physical growth, can help prevent non-communicable diseases such as obesity, and is important to support optimal psychological development, social routines and the development of lifelong eating habits and food preferences.^{2,3,4}

At the time of writing, Yorkshire's National Child Measurement Programme (NCMP) reception-level obesity rates and the presence of dental caries (tooth decay caused by sugars in the diet) indicate that poor diets have a health impact on children in the EY. 22.5% of Yorkshire children are starting school living with obesity or overweight and 27% of five-year-olds have dental decay.⁵ NCMP data are often focused on as a marker for child health in the context of school-aged children; however, there is much less focus on what happens in the first 1,000 days.

In 2023, 140,900 children were registered to attend childcare in Yorkshire EYS.⁶ Data from 2019 suggested that, in England, three quarters of children were in some form of childcare in term time,⁷ many of whom will eat a significant proportion of their daily calories during their time there. If a child eats all their meals in an EYS (breakfast, lunch and dinner), this food provision could make up to 90% of their caloric intake for the day.⁸ Nesta has predicted that childcare reform could result in a 46% rise in the number of hours toddlers spend in EYS by 2028.⁹ Therefore, there is a pressing need to understand how 0-5s are being fed, the barriers and enablers that influence how the EY food system works, and what stakeholders believe could promote change.

We conducted research using a combination of approaches (desk-based research, interviews and menus analysis) to understand first-hand, from those involved in the EYS supply chain, the experiences of procurement and food provision in various EYS types.

Executive summary

Findings:

We discovered that there was a strong will and desire to provide local, Yorkshire food, but that stakeholders felt cost, funding and logistics presented considerable barriers. Notable operational barriers also existed. For example, in state-maintained settings, where food was managed by local authorities, procurement rules were likely to prioritise cost over quality and did not facilitate the use of local suppliers. Some settings had negative experiences of trying to procure local food. There was also a concern about investing in local food that children might not eat, especially during the cost-of-living crisis.

Progress was hampered by a lack of leadership, resources and funding for EY nutrition within local authorities and a prioritisation of school food over EY food. There was a lack of monitoring and accountability for EY food in settings and low adherence to guidance. Wider issues in the sector such as consolidation, the workforce crisis and incoming childcare reform made prioritising nutrition difficult for settings.

Stakeholders recognised the richness of food production within Yorkshire. An enabler example was the presence of a dedicated nursery chef, with a strong focus on local and sustainable food. NGO programmes, such as Vitamin Angels, which provided weekly deliveries of healthy food for nurseries also had a positive influence on a setting being able to procure local fruit and vegetables.

In FixOurFood's schools report,¹ local authorities were identified as the 'heart of many public sector food supply chains into school meals'. It also identified dynamic procurement as an opportunity area. The findings fed into the 2022 Government Buying Standards Consultation.

This case study, however, indicates that the EY sector was much more fragmented, with less easily identifiable entry points for change. Unlike school food, there are no Government Buying Standards in the EY.¹⁰ There was a lack of political will and prioritisation for the EY,¹¹ although the Labour Party's 2023/24 EY review¹² indicates that this may be on the political agenda.

This case study engaged with a small proportion of the EY food system actors in Yorkshire and provided important insights. It built a picture of food provision and procurement from nursery age through to the end of school.

Recommendations:

The findings led to a set of recommendations for policy, advocacy and research (Section 5). Policy recommendations include:

- EY nutrition to be a political priority across government and local authorities
- Government should adequately fund nutrition in EY settings with a dedicated funding stream
- Ofsted to take a more regulated approach to monitoring and accountability
- Government and local authorities should support EY professionals with nutritional training

Background

EY nutrition policy inertia

The EY have been talked about as the 'Cinderella sector'¹² – easily forgotten and deemed less important than schools – and this is reflected in the approaches to nutrition policy and practice. For school food, there are formal advocacy groups, such as the School Food Review, (a consortium of 40 organisations looking to improve the school food system).¹³ Additionally, research from the Local Government Association in 2023 indicated a lack of forums, meetings and sessions for EY in which staff can collaborate, share and learn about EY nutrition.¹¹

Even though discussion on EY has been limited for many years, there was a ramping up of political will in 2023, likely due to the impending election and the finding that 42% of UK voters believed that childcare reform would influence their voting priorities.¹⁴ The first of the current government's childcare reforms (where working parents of 2-year-olds are eligible for 15 hours of free childcare per week) came into force in April 2024.

There were some concerns from settings about their ability to cope with the additional requirements, specifically about income and expenditure ratios and the impact on flexible spend areas like food. The government also stated that reform was 'no easy task'.¹⁵

Furthermore, amid much of the political noise in the EY, there has been little discussion of nutrition and what children will eat in settings. There has also been little discussion on quality, provenance or quantity. Food and its potential impact on child health have not been on the agenda.

Background

A fragmented sector operating in crisis

The EY childcare sector is often described as one “in crisis”.^{16,17} This is anecdotally referenced as a ‘triple-threat’, with the sector impacted by the pandemic, the workforce crisis and the cost-of-living crisis. These threats also have an impact on food provision. By the nature of the sector being split into state-maintained settings, private and voluntary institutions (PVI) and childminders there are also multiple complex procurement arrangements in EYS. Settings can be local authority catered, packed lunch only, privately catered, have food-in house, or no food offer. There are also large chain nurseries that can operate with economies of scale.

Figure 1 indicates national variation in food provision across these settings. For example, 79% of childminders provide food, whereas, in state-maintained settings, 41% of the food is provided by external caterers.¹⁸

Food provision can also differ across the day – some settings offer lunch only, some offer breakfast, lunch, snacks and a ‘teatime’ or dinner meal.

Figure 1: National food provision according to EYS type (Source: Gov.uk)¹⁸

Research approach and aims

Approach

FixOurFood commissioned Bremner & Co to undertake a case study report to explore and map EY food procurement across Yorkshire. This included a literature review, policy review, and qualitative research on system shapers in the field of EY nutrition in Yorkshire. The aim was to learn first-hand from nursery managers, chefs, caterers, procurers, the government and local authorities about their lived experience of feeding 0–5-year-olds and their thoughts on how to change the system for the better. It follows the journey of food provision in settings and examines various procurement avenues. The 16 stakeholders we spoke to were asked about policy, provision, supply chains, tendering and contracting, operational delivery, monitoring and reporting.

Stakeholders interviewed were all Yorkshire-based or had experience of procuring or catering in Yorkshire. They included representatives from:

- Local Authority Public Health teams
- Local Authority Procurement teams
- A Local Authority Catering and Food Technical team
- A Local Authority EY PVI lead
- PVI nursery managers
- PVI nursery chefs
- A headteacher in a state-maintained setting

- A Children’s Centre
- A large caterer with sites in Yorkshire
- A procurement expert
- Government (Yorkshire-remit)

The report is contextualised by a snapshot of child health data in Yorkshire, insights into the fragmented makeup of EYS and an overview of monitoring and data. It incorporates menu analysis of 20 EYS across Yorkshire, using publicly available information on nursery websites. Finally, this research sought to explain how these factors affect the consistent offering and consumption of healthy, sustainable and local nutritious food.

Aims

We aimed to

1. Review the available data on child health in the EY in Yorkshire.
2. Interrogate the Yorkshire EY food system, looking at policy, governance structures, and setting characteristics.
3. Map the monitoring and accountability mechanisms in place for provision of food.
4. Review the procurement and supply chain landscape and engagement in EYS food provision. This incorporated the analysis of EY policies and setting menus.
5. Identify barriers and enablers that hinder and help the development of more local, sustainable food systems.
6. Develop recommendations for further work across policy, advocacy and research.

Methodology

Research used multiple methods, involving two phases, and took an iterative and agile approach, in which each phase informed the direction of travel.

Phase I was a literature and policy review, uncovering the characteristics of EYS in Yorkshire, the procurement and supply chain landscape, and the wider social determinants of health in Yorkshire. This phase was also used to identify key partners and best-practice examples of collaboration. The desk research was complemented by informal meetings with stakeholders from a local authority, catering company, and PVI setting, whose procurement knowledge provided insights into potential barriers.

Phase II involved semi-structured interviews with stakeholders from maintained and PVI settings, a children's centre, the catering sector, a local authority, a regional government body, and menu analysis of 15 PVI and five maintained menus across Yorkshire. This phase was used to validate the insights gathered during Phase I. All interviews were conducted with informed consent and anonymised; therefore, individual interviewees were not listed in this report.

The first section of this report presents a contextual overview of the findings on EY child health in Yorkshire and how the make-up of settings had an impact on food provision. Following this, the policy context for nutrition in the Yorkshire EYS is presented; indicating that EY policy limited access to free nursery meals (FSM) and that there were inadequacies in monitoring and accountability.

We then discuss the evidence about supply chains for the EYS, including operational barriers and enablers.

Finally, menu analysis provided further insights into supply chains and the reported nutritional content of EY food.

Section 1: Findings

We identified many layers of influence in policy and practice on nutrition and procurement in EYS– from wider children’s health policy, EY policy, EY nutrition policy, individual approaches by local authorities to EY and the approach of setting types, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Layers of influences for nutrition and procurement in Yorkshire EYS
(Source: Author’s own)

The research identified consistent systemic and policy barriers to good nutrition and procurement of Yorkshire food in EYS:

- EY nutrition was lower on the agenda than school food, which meant local authorities and governments did not prioritise nutrition in this phase of childhood.
- Eligibility stipulations limited access to nursery FSM and potentially widened health inequalities.
- An EY workforce crisis meant that settings were unable to recruit sufficient staff which impacted the staffing available for food provision. It also made focusing on nutrition difficult in settings with competing demands.
- Insufficient government funding for settings, alongside food inflation and the cost-of-living crisis, made procurement of nutritious food difficult.

1.1 Yorkshire child health, prosperity and inequality

Tooth decay and obesity rates show a pressing need to address diets in the EY

Despite numerous development checks between 0-5 years, there were few data points for the EY in the Public Health Outcomes Framework (the government's framework of public health indicators).¹⁹

What we do know is that Yorkshire had higher than average rates of children living with obesity or overweight (22.5% vs. England 21.3%).²⁰ Yorkshire also had the second highest incidence of dental caries in the UK.

There was a considerable increase in dental caries between 3 and 5 years of age. In Sheffield, dental caries increased from 0.9% at age 3 years to 41% at age 5 years, and from 2.8% to 26.7% in Calderdale in 2020 (Figure 3).²¹

Figure 3: Percentage of children with dental caries in Yorkshire comparing age 3 to age 5 (Source: OHID, 2020)²¹

1.2 Yorkshire settings and food provision

Childcare is a fragmented sector consisting of state-maintained nurseries, PVI's and childminders. In 2023, there were 140,900 children registered for childcare in EYS in Yorkshire.⁶ PVI's comprised most of the registered places (60%), state-maintained 28% and childminders up to 12%²² - see Figure 4. 62% of children were in settings full-time, whereas 15% were in sessional care.²² Children's attendance also varied between sessional care, full-time and some families used a combination of providers.

Figure 4: Number of registered places in EY by provider type in Yorkshire (Source: Gov.uk)²²

Food provision, and therefore, food procurement, differed according to each setting. Settings may be packed lunch only, privately catered, have an in-house chef, or be catered by a local authority. Therefore, unpacking and mapping of this complex sector was challenging.

There was a lack of consistent and reliable data explaining the EY food supply chain across all of Yorkshire's 15 local authorities, where 5,370 providers operate.

There was also a paucity of research and minimal data on the quality or quantity of food in EYS.

1.3 EY nutrition is lower on the agenda

Nutrition in EYS was perceived to be lower on the agenda by the stakeholders we interviewed, who outlined how this directly translated to poorer nutrition outcomes:

In schools, we've got various forums/sessions that we can attend. There's not anything that I know of for EYS. (Local Authority Public Health Team)

When efficiency savings were needed in catering, a 'strict finance manager' came in and cut child food costs. Just EY though, not school food. (Local Authority Catering Manager)

It's just not seen as a priority by locally elected members and in strategic planning. It's all about schools. (Government - Yorkshire lead)

Many local authorities discussed how they wanted to focus on EY nutrition, but a broader lack of funding for EY limited their ability. Further up the chain, local authorities also lacked cabinet members or council leaders to act as champions. It was seen as outside the scope, particularly as there are limited Public Health outcome metrics to report.

It's outside the mandated scope. (Local Authority Public Health Team)

Similar to the national picture, our research indicated that Yorkshire was experiencing a workforce and funding crisis. The number of providers in Yorkshire decreased by 7.5% from 2022 to 2023,²³ and government data indicated that nursery closures were much higher in areas of deprivation.²⁴

Childcare Sufficiency Assessments across North Yorkshire, Bradford and Doncaster reported issues with the labour market, staffing and consolidation by large providers - the 'recruitment and retention crisis'.^{25,26,27} One impact of this, was that in-house chefs were at risk of losing their employment.

I think we're in the middle of a massive recruitment crisis. And a cook, the person who provides the food is the first extra to go. (Local Authority PVI lead)

While settings experienced issues with underfunding and staffing, local authorities also experienced funding cuts. Therefore, there were often insufficient resources to focus on each setting type. PVIs, which make up 60% of the registered places,²² were often not a focus area for local authorities. These issues were compounded by a lack of nutrition specific training.

There's a lack of nutrition training for staff. (Government - Yorkshire Lead)

Settings indicated that, in terms of outcome measures, school readiness and oral health (as opposed to nutrition) were a core focus. Oral health also became a political focus, in 2024 Kier Starmer, the leader of the Labour Party, calling for increased focus on children's oral health in schools.²⁸ This demonstrates policy incoherence, with no focus on food intake, but rather on post-eating hygiene.

There seems to be a lot more about oral health rather than nutrition, about artificial sweeteners. It kind of confuses us because we're all about nutrition. (PVI Nursery Manager)

It's all about school readiness, getting them there. People might not even consider nutrition. (PVI Nursery Manager)

1.4 Inequality of access

In addition to health outcomes, it is also important to consider regional inequity within the Yorkshire child food and health system. Yorkshire had the second highest number of children under 16 living in absolute poverty (21.5%),²⁹ yet only 5% of EY Yorkshire children were registered as eligible for FSM in EY settings (versus a national figure of 8%).³⁰ Only children in state-maintained settings (28% of the registered places) were eligible, and entitlement criteria stipulated that children must attend before and after lunch.

This may have a greater impact on families living in disadvantage, whose children might be unable to stay in nurseries for that length of time.³¹ Also, some settings only offered morning or afternoon sessions. In addition to a low eligibility rate, take-up of nursery FSM was only 55%, Nationally. Across Yorkshire, the data was incomplete, but the rate varied from 30% in North Yorkshire, 54% in Kingston upon Hull, to 100% in York.²²

Some of the local authorities said that close to 100% of their settings were PVLs, meaning none of the children in that authority would have access to FSM, even if they were living in poverty. However, interviewees outlined how settings would feed children who were in obvious need, despite not falling within the eligibility criteria.

For our FSM children, we'll make a jacket potato or a healthy sandwich. And then with those families who are struggling, we will make the food for them. (Headteacher – State-maintained nursery)

1.5 What are children eating in EYS and how is it monitored?

Evidence and data gaps about nutrition in the EY

In terms of monitoring and accountability, Ofsted was the policy lead for monitoring the quality of nutrition in EYS, and EYS are obligated to adhere to the guidance in the Early Years Foundation Stage Framework (EYFS), which stipulated that food must be 'healthy, balanced, and nutritious'³²; however, there is very little data or evidence on what children eat in EYS.

A recent review³³ identified that, in England, larger portion sizes in EYS were associated with greater food and energy intake, and a 2023 study of portion sizes in EYS highlighted that caterers served the same size portion for EY children as they did for school-aged children.³⁴ There are also various other guidance documents, such as the voluntary Eat Better Start Better Guidance,³⁵ and guidance and menus from Public Health England.³⁶ A cross-sectional study by the London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine in 2024 indicated that, although 82% of settings are aware of such guidance, only 48.8% use them – predominantly as they 'know what is healthy without them'.³⁷

A study with Rotherham Childminders also indicated that food was 'not consistent with dietary guidelines' and one childminder argued that government guidance for the EY 'doesn't hit the mark'.³⁸ In our research, some interviewees decided to adhere to their own self-defined nutritional principles and many echoed the complexity of available guidance.

(Do settings follow guidelines?). I'd like to say yes, but in austerity, they do what they can. (Local Authority – PVI Lead)

We stick to the early nutritional principle that the meals have to be nutritious and wholesome. (Nursery Chef)

For one local authority, Ofsted's role in monitoring nutrition in the EY meant that they no longer performed quality checks.

We no longer have teams that go in to do quality checks with providers, because government said Ofsted were the arbiters of quality. Previously we'd quite often stay and have lunch. In Ofsted reports, I don't think the actual quality of food is mentioned. (Local Authority Public Health Team)

Previous research identified that many local authorities predominantly focus on state-maintained settings.¹¹ Only one of the local authority teams we spoke to were engaged specifically with PVIs and had dedicated staff, established EY collaboration forums and actively communicated with settings.

We assume that the nurseries are feeding their children relatively well. Maybe that's not an assumption we should be making. (Local Authority Public Health Team)

1.5 What are children eating in EYS and how is it monitored?

We don't necessarily engage with private providers as much. (Local Authority Public Health Team)

I couldn't comment much on the food that's being served by childminders. (Local Authority Public Health Team)

In terms of monitoring and accountability, our interviewees outlined that local authorities developed their own suite of tools to work with settings in the absence of a government strategy. For example, North Yorkshire County Council had a Skills Mix team that works with EY practitioners and sent out monthly messages to providers featuring healthy eating.³⁹

Many interviewees referred to several self-accreditation award schemes available to EYS, such as the Healthy Schools Award. This scheme was run by individual authorities, and the award process often took the form of self-assessment followed by an audit by the local authority. One local authority funded accreditation to all settings in the area. However, for other PVIs, this was a traded service provided by local authorities. Another award scheme mentioned by many interviewees and well-regarded by one local authority was HENRY.⁴⁰

While there was some positivity about these schemes, some argued that they were onerous for settings and local authorities to manage and lacked compliance or monitoring. They felt that their parents were not interested in whether the settings were accredited.

These council-developed awards don't get any gravitas, do they? Because no one really cares if they've got one. And it was hard to incentivise and motivate settings. (Local Authority Public Health Team)

Awards come at a cost. Usually, you pay for specific awards - if we got a food award for buying fresh and local, our parents wouldn't really care. (PVI Nursery Manager)

Even when benefits were identified, we learnt that the cost of signing up and completing the award was identified as a barrier. For example, one local authority setting received funding for an NGO award to develop a 'whole setting' approach to food. The interviewee described having a positive experience, referring to benefits, such as assistance with menu design. However, they noted that the cost was prohibitive and unsustainable.

We took part in a funded pilot. It was such a fantastic scheme - it really helped them look at where they got their food from and to balance their menus. But it didn't take in consideration the amount of money, it was idealistic, and it didn't support them. (Local Authority PVI lead)

1.6 The complex EY supply chain

Stakeholders in our research demonstrated a desire to buy local food and a recognition of the richness of the Yorkshire food system. For settings that were able to buy locally, there was also joy in being able to 'pinpoint which boat the fish came from' (PVI nursery chef).

One of the reasons that I love working here is because we've got that locality and that provenance - we can trace everything, and we work with local suppliers to get the best ingredients that we can. (PVI Nursery Chef)

However, regardless of whether food was procured through a local authority caterer, provided in-house catered, or packed lunch only, stakeholders talked about five operational barriers to the procurement of local and sustainable food. These are detailed below and include:

- Funding and food costs
- Scalability and supplier sourcing
- Tendering and procurement
- Staffing/resources
- Child preferences

1.7 Funding and food costs

Lack of funding and cost of food hampers progress

Funding differs significantly between provider types; for example, national data indicate that private settings spend 4% of their total costs on food and a maintained nursery school just 1% of total costs on food²² (see Table 1). There is no set per meal rate for EY food, and no funding line for food in state-maintained settings.

Table 1: Food spend in EYS (Source: Gov.uk, 2023)²²

Provider type	% of total costs
Private group-based	5%
Voluntary group-based	2%
School-based provider offering nursery	2%
Maintained nursery school	1%
Childminders	11%

Amongst our interviewees, cost was perceived to be the greatest hurdle, not only to providing nutritious and delicious food more generally, but also to making sure that food could be derived locally from Yorkshire. This was recognised by government representatives ('so, it's certainly cost' - Government, Yorkshire lead), across all settings and within local authorities.

It's important to buy local, but that comes at a price. I think it's affordability. (PVI Nursery Manager)

I think there is a will, but it comes down to cost and feasibility versus going to Tesco. (Local Authority - PVI Lead)

One setting was only able to procure local fruits and vegetables with the financial assistance of an NGO, who partly funded their food offer. Another got food from FareShare.⁴¹ Getting food donations from organisations such as FareShare has been echoed in previous research, undertaken by the Local Government Association.¹¹ However, supermarkets are focused on reducing their food waste⁴² which puts pressure on the supply to food aid organisations and may impact this provision.

We're lucky that we have NGO support (£150 worth of food every week). If we didn't have that, I think we would struggle because food is such an expense. I don't think we'd be able to do the level of menu and the nutritional value that we do without that subsidy. (PVI Nursery Manager)

1.7 Funding and food costs

Lack of funding and cost of food hampers progress

Some interviewees spoke about how underfunding directly affected their choice of food provision. One setting used to supply food but found it financially unsustainable and now only allows packed lunches. We do not have data on the nutritional standards of packed lunches in the EY but evidence from the University of Leeds suggested that only 1% of school packed lunches meet nutritional standards⁴³

In our other smaller setting, we now unfortunately only have the option for children to bring a packed lunch. We support families to put good stuff in their children's lunches. (Headteacher - State-Maintained Nursery)

Many local authorities spoke about funding rates being a barrier to consistently delivering good nutrition in settings:

Our funding rate is one of the lowest in the county. (Local Authority, PVI Lead.)

There also seems to be a divergence in opinion regarding the experiences between PVIs and local authorities – with one local authority considering that the PVIs had more financial freedom and, therefore, food procurement was easier for them. This differed from the feedback we received from the PVIs we interviewed, who felt unable to spend a lot of money on food or facilitate local and sustainable food.

Funding makes things difficult though. In the past 10 years there has been an efficiency drive to cut costs. At one point we were asked to 'do the PVI model' for EY which is a 30hr one-cook per nursery affair. But we can't compete with PVIs - they do it cheaper and they are private companies which make profit. EY PVIs can run their catering and spend a lot of money, all organic. We'd love to do that, but the budget doesn't run to that. (Local Authority Catering Manager)

The cost of the food here or in any nursery is quite substantial because of the procedure that you have to go through. It is just the rising costs of everything. (PVI Nursery Chef)

In the state-maintained settings, where the nurseries form part of a school setting, local authorities indicated that provision and guidance mirror that of schools. Previous evidence suggested that in this circumstance, portion sizes are also matched, meaning a 0-5 child has the same portion as a school-aged child, which may contribute to issues with energy intake.^{33,34}

Where nurseries are attached to school provision, they almost form part of that provision. Most policies would apply to the EYS as well. They mirror that food provision that's provided. (Local Authority)

1.8 Scalability and supplier sourcing - 'It's just easier to get it from Tesco'

Settings find local supply chains hard to access

Several interviewees spoke about the complexity of attempting to procure local food in nursery settings. An example of this was having to talk to multiple suppliers, which created an unnecessary strain on resources at a time when the EY workforce was already experiencing significant capacity issues. However, there were examples of individual settings seeking out local fruit, vegetable, and fish suppliers.

It's a case of finding a local supplier that can fulfil the order and has a decent range of products. We've got a greengrocer a couple of miles down the road who supplies us with all the fresh vegetables and fruit. I've got a fish supplier in Huddersfield who does the fish and they work with local fishermen. (PVI Nursery Chef)

A further barrier was not being able to find a supplier who would supply individual settings – or what were described as 'minimum order challenges'. Larger chain nurseries have scale and, therefore, are attractive propositions for potential suppliers.

Our research indicated that for smaller, non-chain nurseries, order quantity was not sufficient to attract suppliers. Furthermore, ordering from multiple suppliers was resource-intensive.

I have tried before to get local businesses to deliver us fruit and vegetables and I wanted to go down the seasonal route. They're just not interested, unfortunately. (Headteacher - State-Maintained Setting)

We have tried in the past trying to get fresh fruit and veg from a local supplier, but we were ordering from loads of different places. It was just getting a little bit confusing. And the price was just, it was extortionate, so our Director stopped that. (PVI Nursery Manager)

For many, these complexities meant it was easier to order through local supermarkets and top this up with food from local shops.

We do all the ordering weekly. We do an online Sainsbury's order, and then we have a local shop. (PVI Nursery Manager)

1.9 Tendering and procurement

Operational barriers prevent the procurement of locally sourced food

For local authority-led settings, there was a strong desire to use local and seasonal food, but interviewees talked about bureaucratic barriers, such as internal procurement regulations and tendering restrictions, which made this unfeasible. These barriers were also confirmed by the catering organisation we interviewed and identified in FixOurFood's work on procurement in schools.¹

We've got a supplier and I think that procurement looked down on it. (Children's Centre)

We do sometimes get nursery schools that want us to source from the farm shop down the road. We can't do that because our food is audited. (National Caterer – With Yorkshire sites)

Local authorities felt there were opportunities for local food to take higher priority as social value becomes more important. That, however, this was felt to rely on the 'personal values of whoever is in charge,' (Local Authority Catering Manager). The fact that local procurement may not be mandated within council procurement contracts meant there was less impetus to prioritise it.

There are challenges to bidding to supply to a council – procurement, social value, etc. A small local supplier would find it quite difficult. We're limited by the Public Contracts Regulations, 2015. We do specify to source locally where possible – fruit and veg based in Yorkshire etc, work with local growers etc. (Local Authority Food Technical Officer)

There's lots of conversations with providers about investing in local but when it comes to buying food for the caterers, they are solely driven by cost and constrained. (Local Authority Catering Manager)

The children's centre interviewed in our research were honest about their level of interest in local procurement, which was influenced primarily by ease and convenience. Their feedback shows there is an opportunity for organisations such as FixOurFood to work with the EY sector to demonstrate the benefits of local food in the EY.

(Is food provenance important to you?)

Yeah, if I'm totally honest, probably not. It's easier for us to drop an email to this company. (Children's Centre)

1.9 Tendering and procurement

The procurement expert who was interviewed discussed 'dynamic procurement' - an electronic procurement system that operates in an open market where multiple suppliers can participate. For them, dynamic procurement would be a great opportunity and an enabler for EYS to enter more sustainable supply chains; but again, the perception of complexity is a barrier.

People tend to think that dynamic food procurement is going to be far more complicated than it is. All you're doing is digitising the chain that you've already got and bringing more transparency to it. (Procurement Expert)

Alongside the opportunities that a focus on social value might bring, interviewees thought that local authority food strategies may provide opportunities to influence local nursery food procurement in Yorkshire. Some interviewees were working on their own strategies and recognised that the increased focus on climate change may have good synergies with food in institutions like EYS.

The food strategy is very much a holistic system strategy. It's about sustainable food. It's about farm to fork conversations. (Local Authority Public Health Team)

Locally sourced food - yes, it is something that is very important to our local authority. We are delivering a lot of work around climate and looking at where food comes from. I know that our caterers have been looking into the carbon footprint of their menus. (Local Authority Catering Manager)

1.10 Staffing/resources

Workforce crisis impacts settings ability to focus on EY nutrition

Many of our interviewees discussed how having insufficient staff was a barrier to good EY nutrition. One setting referenced how they felt lucky to have an in-house chef who would take on the onus of food ordering ('it's a huge undertaking' – Yorkshire PVI setting) but recognised that having a qualified and diligent chef came at a cost. For many, this impact of underfunding meant that staff members who are not trained in nutrition, cook nursery food.

There's a huge impact of not enough money - not just for food, but to pay for somebody to cook the food. What we're seeing is managers, deputy chairs, random members of staff doing the cooking, but their focus should be somewhere else. Everyone should have somebody who's qualified and trained to do the cooking. (Local Authority – PVI lead)

1.11 Child and parent preference and feeding children

Child and parent preferences impact appetite for locally sourced food

One of the other areas raised in the research was that there were barriers faced by disadvantaged families and settings in areas of deprivation to prioritising local food.

You want to buy local, organic; you want to know where it's coming from, but we're in an area of deprivation. It's not a priority to our children, our parents. (PVI Nursery Manager)

Interviewees also expressed a fear of wastage within settings, particularly during the cost-of-living crisis and considering food inflation. They were not keen on putting resources and effort into local and sustainable fruit, vegetables and proteins when the children might refuse the provision offer.

The ultimate barrier is children not eating it. They love curry, rice, pasta, pizza... (Headteacher - State-Maintained Setting)

Some representatives from EYS indicated that it was a struggle to get children to eat well and that this had progressively worsened over time.

Children are getting worse with the food they're eating. It's having a big impact on us as a setting because behaviour is challenging. Children's health is getting harder to manage. (PVI Nursery Manager)

1.12 The language of provenance and local food

Is it local enough?

Several interviewees from EYS told us that they bought local fruits and vegetables. However, they were not necessarily able to guarantee that they were from Yorkshire. This confusion/lack of clarification regarding whether food was truly local was mentioned by several interviewees.

We use a local fruit and veg supplier. I can't necessarily promise that all of his fruit and veggies are from the local area. The challenge is finding somewhere that's a true local supplier rather than just a wholesaler. (PVI Nursery Chef)

When I've done previous tenders, that's been a big thing about local, but is it the supply that's local or the producer that is local? If we can say our carrots come from Yorkshire, is that local enough? Whereas Yorkshire is quite a big area. It could come from North Yorkshire to South Yorkshire. Is that enough? (National Caterer - with Yorkshire sites).

Section 2: Menu analysis

How do nursery menus help us increase our understanding of the procurement journey and provision?

Overall view

The menus we analysed were heterogeneous, with a great deal of variation between settings in terms of the details of food provided. Menus did not seem to be regularly updated, and it was not always clear whether menus were examples or the menu of the week, for example. Some settings were extremely specific to food provision – listing specific vegetables, such as peas/parsnips, whereas others just listed 'seasonal vegetables' or 'healthy food.'

Of the settings which had websites, half mentioned healthy eating within their pages, using language such as 'healthy', 'nutritious' and 'balanced', (aligned with the EYFS Framework). There was little evidence of settings publicly promoting a 'whole-setting approach', such as eating together or focusing on development, and none of the settings published food policies on their websites, though this may well occur in settings but not be documented.

Procurement and provision

In terms of food provenance, 20% of menus mentioned using local food, but none of the nurseries mentioned using food specifically from Yorkshire. Only 15% of the menus mentioned the use of UK produce. The menus referred to seasonality more regularly. Only three nurseries provided information on their external suppliers.

The menu analysis suggested that food provision was predominantly undertaken in-house; of the 12 settings that provided this information, 10 had in-house nursery cooks/chefs. Two state-maintained settings outsourced food provision to a local authority caterer and parish school. 95% of the settings did not specify how many of the lunches consisted of packed lunches, and only one nursery had a robust packed lunch policy with parent information and 'strict guidance'. According to this policy, if food does not meet the guidelines, the child's meal will be replaced with a nursery meal.

Section 2: Menu analysis

Guidance and quality

None of the menus that we analysed mentioned 'Eat Better Start Better' nor the School Food Standards. However, some referred to other standards, including the Food Standards Agency (FSA), NHS Startwell and 'EY nutritional guidance'. These findings echo earlier research², showing that there is confusion and reticence in using government-issued voluntary guidance. The menus and settings' websites rarely mentioned award schemes: three out of 20 listed their FSA (food hygiene) or equivalent ratings, two had local council-specific ratings, one was NHS accredited, and one had a Food for Life award. Award schemes were not used as selling points - 65% of the settings didn't mention awards.

Portion size is a focus of the Eat Better Start Better guidelines, but it was not mentioned within any of the menus we analysed. There was some evidence of wholegrain-starchy foods being served, but these tended to be in the form of pasta, pizza, rice and breads. Most settings seemed to meet the guidelines in terms of the provision of vegetables, and many offered fruits, such as snacks, seasonal fruits and crudités. The importance of fruits and vegetables was evident across the menus.

There was also evidence of sugary desserts, chocolates and heavy puddings. For example, one setting offered Angel Delight, chocolate cupcakes and rocky roads as desserts for three days across a two-week cycle. The provision of desserts was raised as an area of concern by several interviewees.

You know, there's a bit too much cake and custard. (Headteacher - State-Maintained Setting)

Best practice

Two out of the 15 PVI chain settings whose menus were analysed exemplified best practice. One referenced their suppliers, had a dedicated catering team and was accredited by Startwell, an NHS nutrition scheme led by the local authority.

It did not offer a dessert if there was a starter and the dessert often consisted of fruits. It offered vegetarian meals two days a week, used free-range eggs and followed the Marine Conservation Society 'fish to avoid' list.

The other setting reported using on-site chefs with experience in nutrition, food hygiene and menu planning, and offered varied menus reflecting different cultures. It focused on children having a healthy relationship with food, where a meal is a shared social experience. Some of its settings also had their own allotments, where the children could help grow produce, and some took the children on trips to local stores to buy food.

Section 3: Barriers and enablers to the procurement of locally sourced, nutritious, affordable Yorkshire food

Table 2: Barriers and enablers which affect the consistent offering and consumption of healthy, sustainable and local nutritious food (Source: Author's own)

Barriers
Lack of political will and government support for the EY sector
Prioritisation of school food over EY food
Staffing/resourcing and capacity
Funding and food costs
Lack of local authority support for PVLs
Minimum order challenges due to EYS size
Box-ticking and procurement barriers

Enablers
Better local authority and government support for nutrition in the EY
Dedicated EY leads within local authorities
Dedicated resources within settings – chefs/cooks and adequate nutrition training for EY professionals
3rd sector funding support to enable settings to procure locally sourced food
Engaged policy teams within local authorities who support all settings
Dynamic procurement which overcomes minimum order challenges
An overarching food strategy which encompasses 0-5s and the procurement of local and sustainable food

Section 4: Conclusions

The supply chain differs considerably between settings. However, for many local authorities, if the setting is attached to a school, it followed a school food provision route. There is opportunity here, therefore, to influence via school food procurement routes. For many nurseries, shopping at local supermarkets was a normal procurement process.

A challenge raised is that the voluntary standards aren't fit for purpose and are often not used. While self-accreditation is a well-used intervention, there have been reservations about its efficacy and monitoring effectiveness.

The stakeholders were clear that cost, workforce crisis and underfunding were the main barriers preventing them from following a more locally sourced procurement. Some settings had negative experiences with local procurement, including issues around minimum order expectations, ease of purchase and cost.

The EY sector is struggling to cope with existing conditions and, while increasing the use of local food was seen as a worthy goal, it felt unreachable. There are also perceived societal barriers such as children's food preferences and parental support.

Section 5: Policy and research recommendations

Many of the representatives we spoke to found it difficult to articulate what researchers and organisations could do to support them in delivering best practice nutrition in EYS, predominantly because the sector felt themselves to be in fire-fighting mode and were just 'doing the best they can' (Yorkshire State-Maintained Setting).

There are, however, several recommendations that can be drawn from this research to influence healthy, sustainable, and local nutritious food in the EYS. These require collaboration from actors across government, local authorities, and organisations such as FixOurFood.

Policy

National government should:

- Politically prioritise EY nutrition in settings. EY falls under the Minister for Children and Families, and covers inspection, regulation, literacy and numeracy and FSM⁴⁴ but not food in EYS. Food in EYS should be explicitly recognised and considered a focus area, particularly considering childcare reform and the increase in the number of children who will be eating in settings.
- Include EYS nutrition in any review of the Government Buying Standards.
- Fund nutrition in EYS with a dedicated food funding stream.
- Review the stipulations on EYS FSM eligibility (where children must attend before and after lunch to get FSM) to ensure that those in need of support have access to a hot lunch.
- Instruct Ofsted to take a more regulated approach to monitoring and accountability in EYS and for EYS guidance to be reviewed for efficacy and practicality. This could be done as part of the FSA's School Food compliance pilot.⁴⁵
- Implement nutritional training for all EYS professionals working with existing bodies such as the Early Years Alliance.
- Undertake a new Childcare and Early Years Provider survey (the last one was in 2019) which includes barriers to supporting good EY nutrition. This should be across all settings and not just those that are state-maintained.

Section 5: Policy and research recommendations

Advocacy

Organisations advocating for improvement in EY nutrition should:

- Improve collaboration across the sector – with Yorkshire local authorities and organisations, such as FixOurFood, creating and nurturing forums in which to share best practice and advocate for children in EYS.
- Engage policymakers on EYS nutrition and to advocate for EYS nutrition to be included in Yorkshire local authorities' food strategies.
- Demonstrate the benefits of locally-grown, sustainable food.
- Work on messaging and clarification of what local means, and what the benefits are of following this procurement route.

Further research

- Gather more evidence from local authorities regarding who caters for children in EYS, particularly around tendering and procurement barriers. Investigate what would enable the stipulation of local and seasonally grown food within tender contracts.
- Undertake further research to obtain baseline data on the quality of food in EYS.
- Review opportunities for local procurement pilots with settings, either through dynamic procurement, procurement hubs, or collaboration with existing school procurement.

Section 6: Limitations

Research limitations

Although drawing on data from a limited number of stakeholders, in what is a fragmented sector, it was possible to begin mapping theoretical generalisations on the wider sector. There was also a good range of views from different actors in the system. The structure of the analysis draws on qualitative examples and case studies of specific locations or points in the supply chain. This is underpinned by a wider food system lens, uncovering the challenges and barriers in delivering economic value, health outcomes and sustainability.

The menu analysis had some limitations. First, the quantitative observations were limited by the variation in menu detail and structure, meaning that menus could not be compared as like-for-like. For example, they differed in terms of the meals available (breakfast, lunch or tea) or the description of foods ('vegetables available' vs. parsnip, peas) and dietary alternatives provided ('alternatives available' vs. a detailed listing of the vegetarian offering). Second, the settings did not refer to the standards that they adhered to. Therefore, it was not feasible to judge them against the Eat Better Start Better or School Food Standards. The extent to which the menus were live or representative examples was also unclear. Without accompanying observational visits, it was not possible to confirm whether the reported menus matched food provision in practice. Finally, some data were taken from the settings' food and nutrition pages. However, this was not possible for all settings, making direct comparison difficult.

References

1. FixOurFood (2022) *Public Sector Food Procurement Supply Chains leading to School Meals: The Case of Yorkshire*. Available at: <https://ukfoodsystems.ukri.org/research-projects-training-reports/public-sector-food-procurement-supply-chains-leading-to-school-meals-the-case-of-york> (Accessed: 23 January 2024).
2. Warren, E., Williams, L. and Knai, C. (2022) 'The "Cinderella sector": The challenges of promoting food and nutrition for young children in early years' settings in England', *Ecology of Food and Nutrition*, 61(5), pp. 576–594. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/03670244.2022.2073353> (Accessed 30 January 2024).
3. Obesity Health Alliance (2021) *Turning the Tide*. Available at: <https://obesityhealthalliance.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/Turning-the-Tide-A-10-year-Healthy-Weight-Strategy.pdf> (Accessed 1 February 2024).
4. Academy of Medical Sciences (2024) Prioritising early childhood to promote the nation's health, wellbeing and prosperity. Available at: <https://acmedsci.ac.uk/file-download/16927511> (Accessed 7 February 2024).
5. OHID (2022/3) Obesity Profile: Yorkshire and the Humber. Available at: <https://fingertips.phe.org.uk/national-child-measurement-programme#page/1/gid/8000011/pat/15/ati/6/are/E12000003/iid/90316/age/200/sex/4/cat/-1/ctp/-1/yr/1/cid/4/tbm/1> (Accessed 28 February 2024)
6. Gov.uk (2024) *Childcare and early years provider survey*. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/statistics/announcements/survey-of-childcare-and-early-years-providers-2024> (Accessed January 2024).
7. Department for Education (2019). *Childcare and Early Years Survey of Parents in England, 2019*. Available at: https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/5dfa2b7140f0b62187a637ef/CEYSP_2019_Report.pdf (Accessed 20 February 2024).
8. Mucavele, P., Wall, C., Whiting, L. (2020) 'Development of HM Government example menus for early years' settings in England' *Nutrition Bulletin*. Available at: https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/epdf/10.1111/nbu.12472?saml_referrer (Accessed: 23 January 2024).
9. Nesta (2023) *Early-years sector needs 27,500 staff to meet 46% rise in hours spent in childcare for toddlers*. Available at: <https://www.nesta.org.uk/press-release/early-years-sector-needs-27500-staff-to-meet-46-rise-in-hours-spent-in-childcare/> (Accessed 20 February 2024).
10. Gov.uk (2021) *Buying for Schools*. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/guidance/buying-for-schools--2> (Accessed January 24 2024).
11. Local Government Association (2023). *Shining a light on early years nutrition: the role of councils*. Available at: <https://www.local.gov.uk/publications/shining-light-early-years-nutrition-role-councils> (Accessed 24 January 2024).
12. Early Years Alliance (2023) *Labour announces plan for new early years review*. Available at: <https://www.eyalliance.org.uk/news/2023/10/labour-announces-plan-new-early-years-review> (Accessed: 24 January 2024).
13. School Food Review (2023) *Manifesto*. Available at: <https://www.schoolfoodmatters.org/what-we-do/campaigns/food-policy/school-food-review> (Accessed 24 January 2024).
14. Early Education and Childcare Coalition (2023) *Pulse Check 2023: Public Attitudes Towards Early Education and Childcare*. Available at: <https://www.earlyeducationchildcare.org/pulse-check> (Accessed: 4 January 2024).
15. Oppenheim, M. (2023) *Government admits criticised new childcare policy is 'no easy task' to implement*. The Independent. 2 January 2024. Available at: <https://www.independent.co.uk/news/uk/home-news/free-childcare-policy-criticism-staffing-b2470448.html> (Accessed 24 January 2024).

References

16. PACEY (2021) *A workforce in crisis – saving our early years*. Available at: [https://www.pacey.org.uk/Pacey/media/Website-files/Non-PACEY%20documents%20\(PDFs\)/a-workforce-in-crisis-saving-our-early-years.pdf](https://www.pacey.org.uk/Pacey/media/Website-files/Non-PACEY%20documents%20(PDFs)/a-workforce-in-crisis-saving-our-early-years.pdf) (Accessed: 24 January 2024)
17. Early Years Educator (2022) Pandemic pushes ‘already fragile’ early years sector into crisis, new report finds.
18. Department for Education and NatCen (2020) *How early years providers support disadvantaged children, children with SEND, the home learning environment and healthy eating*. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/how-early-years-providers-support-children> (Accessed 24 January 2024).
19. Gov.uk (2024) *Public Health Outcomes Framework*. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/collections/public-health-outcomes-framework> (Accessed 8 February 2024).
20. OHID (2023) *Patterns and trends in child obesity in Yorkshire and the Humber*. Available at: <https://fingertips.phe.org.uk/national-child-measurement-programme#page/1/gid/8000011/pat/15/ati/6/are/E12000003/iid/90316/age/200/sex/4/cat/-1/ctp/-1/yr/1/cid/4/tbm/1> (Accessed 4 January 2024).
21. OHID (2020) *Child and maternal health – oral statistics*. Available at: <https://fingertips.phe.org.uk/profile/child-health-profiles/data#page/1/gid/1938133228>. (Accessed 4 January 2024).
22. Gov.uk (2023) *Childcare and early years provider survey*. Available at: <https://explore-education-statistics.service.gov.uk/find-statistics/childcare-and-early-years-provider-survey> (Accessed 15 January 2024).
23. Gov.uk (2024) *Childcare and early years provider survey*. Available at: <https://explore-education-statistics.service.gov.uk/find-statistics/childcare-and-early-years-provider-survey> (Accessed January 2024). NB: Comparison between 2022 data and 2023 data.
24. Ofsted (2022) *Main findings: childcare providers and inspections as at 31 March 2022*. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/statistics/childcare-providers-and-inspections-as-at-31-march-2022/main-findings-childcare-providers-and-inspections-as-at-31-march-2022#:~:text=Most%20recent%20inspections%20of%20providers, had%20received%20a%20full%20inspection.&text=At%20their%20most%20recent%20inspection%2C%2096%25%20of%20all%20childcare%20providers, point%20since%2031%20August%202021> (Accessed 24 January 2024).
25. Doncaster Council (2022) *Childcare Sufficiency Assessment 2022*. Available at: <https://www.doncaster.gov.uk/Documents/DocumentView/Stream/Media/Default/ChildrenYoungPeopleFamilies/Documents/2022%20Doncaster%20Childcare%20Sufficiency%20Assessment.pdf> (Accessed 11 January 2024).
26. City of Bradford (2022) Early Education and Childcare Sufficiency Assessment. Available at: <https://www.bradford.gov.uk/children-young-people-and-families/looking-for-childcare/childcare-sufficiency-assessment/> (Accessed 11 January 2024).
27. North Yorkshire County Council (2021) *Childcare Sufficiency Assessment 2021*. Available at: <https://cyps.northyorks.gov.uk/sites/default/files/Early%20years/Sufficiency/2021%20CSA%20Report.pdf> (Accessed 11 January 2024).
28. Crerar, P. and Weale, S. (2024) *Starmer to embrace ‘nanny state’ with plan for toothbrushing in schools*. 10 January. The Guardian. 10 January 2024. Available at: <https://www.theguardian.com/society/2024/jan/10/keir-starmer-announces-plan-for-supervised-toothbrushing-in-schools> (Accessed: 30 January 2024).
29. OHID (2021/2022) *Public Health Outcomes Framework – Geography Yorkshire and the Humber*. Available at: <https://fingertips.phe.org.uk/profile/public-health-outcomes-framework> (Accessed 11 January 2024).
30. Gov.uk (2022/3) *School Pupils and their Characteristics*: Available at: <https://explore-education-statistics.service.gov.uk/data-tables/permalink/d142e459-ad7a-4d4c-c706-08dc2e333b3f> (Accessed 15 January 2024).

References

31. Education Policy Institute (2024) *What's Cooking? A review of evidence and discussion on the Free School Meals (FSM) measure in the National Pupil Database*. Available at: <https://epi.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2024/01/FSM-Report-Strand-1-FINAL-1.pdf> (Accessed 24 January 2024).
32. Gov.uk (2023) *Early years foundation stage (EYFS) statutory framework (2023)*. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/early-years-foundation-stage-framework--2> (Accessed: 24 January 2024).
33. SACN (2023) *Feeding young children aged 1 to 5 years*. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/sacn-report-feeding-young-children-aged-1-to-5-years> (Accessed: 24 January 2024).
34. Pearce, J. and Wall, C.J. (2023) 'School lunch portion sizes provided for children attending early years settings within primary schools: A cross-sectional study', *Journal of Human Nutrition and Dietetics: The Official Journal of the British Dietetic Association*, Issue 36, Volume 5, pp. 1887–1900. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/jhn.13183> (Accessed: 24 January 2024).
35. Foundation Years (2017) *Eat Better, Start Better - Foundation Years*. Available at: <https://foundationyears.org.uk/eat-better-start-better/> (Accessed: 1 January 2024).
36. Public Health England (2017) *Example menus for early years settings in England*. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/example-menus-for-early-years-settings-in-england> (Accessed: 14 January 2024).
37. Warren, E., Boadu, P., Exley, J., Williams, L., Erens, B., Knai, C. (2024) *Knowledge and use of voluntary food and drink guidelines in English nurseries? Results from a nationally representative cross-sectional study. 'Food policy'* Available at: DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodpol.2023.102573> (Accessed 24 January 2024).
38. Goldsborough, N., Homer, C., Atchinson, R., Barker, M.E. (2016) 'Healthy eating in the early years: A qualitative exploration of food provision in the childminder setting', *British Food Journal*, 118(4), pp. 992–1002. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/BFJ-01-2015-0014> (Accessed 25 January 2024).
39. CYPInfo (2023) *Early Years Key Messages*. Available at: <https://cyps.northyorks.gov.uk/early-years-key-messages> (Accessed 25 January 2024).
40. HENRY (2023) *HENRY Home Page*. Available at: <https://www.henry.org.uk/> (Accessed February 18 2024).
41. FareShare (2024) *Homepage*. Available at: <https://fareshare.org.uk/> (Accessed 18 February 2024).
42. SustainabilityBeat (2023) *Supermarket food waste: Is it as bad as Tesco CEO Ken Murphy says?*. Available at: <https://www.sustainability-beat.co.uk/2023/10/13/supermarket-food-waste/> (Accessed 6 March 2024).
43. Evans, C.E.L. Melia, K.E., Rippin, H.L, Hancock, N., Cade, J. (2020) 'A repeated cross-sectional survey assessing changes in diet and nutrient quality of English primary school children's packed lunches between 2006 and 2016', *BMJ Open*, 10(1), p. e029688. Available at: <https://bmjopen.bmj.com/content/bmjopen/10/1/e029688.full.pdf> (Accessed 30 January 2024).
44. Department for Education (2022) *Minister of State (Minister for Children and Families) Responsibilities*. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/ministers/minister-of-state-children-and-families> (Accessed 12 March 2024).
45. FSA (2023) *School Food Standards Compliance Pilot: Discovery and Feasibility Research*. Available at: <https://www.food.gov.uk/research/innovative-regulator/school-food-standards-compliance-pilot-discovery-and-feasibility-research> (Accessed 12 March 2024).

Acknowledgements

FixOurFood is a UKRI-funded Transforming UK Food Systems programme (BB/V004581/1).

This report was funded through a BBSRC Flexible Talent Mobility Account award via the University of York.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.11208136